

Implementation of Training in Improving the Performance of Haimart Store Employess in Kabupaten Boalemo

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the implementation of training in improving employee performance at the Haimart Store, through several indicators, namely: training benefits, training infrastructure, training methods, and training materials as well as knowing the factors that affect employee performance at the Haimart Store with indicators, namely: Internal employee factors and organizational internal environmental factors.

The methods in this study uses descriptive qualitative methods with observation data collection techniques, in-depth interviews, and documentation

The result showed that the implementation of training has benefits for employees or trainees, especially in developing the abilities possessed by the instructors or trainers in this training program, who are the owners and heads of Haimart Stores. The method used is to divide the two training implementations, firstly basic training for new employees and the second employee capability development training for employees who have been placed in the existing divisions at the Haimart Store. The materials used in this training are compiled by the owner of the Haimart Store based on the purpose of implementing the training and development of the Haimart Store. The materials used in this training are compiled by the owner of the Haimart Store based on the purpose of implementing the training and development of the Haimart Store. Although the implementation of training is currently running well, there are still factors that affect performance, including internal employee factors, especially minimal knowledge about the training provided and factors of the internal environment of the organization where there is still a lack of facilities used at the time of training.

Keywords: Training implementation, factors affecting Performance

1. Introduction

In today's modern era, business competition is intensifying and technological sophistication is increasingly developing which will cause companies to be threatened towards changes in organizational management both at the national and international levels. This situation is not only felt by large companies, but small companies also feel the impact of today's technological sophistication. So that employee must be able to adjust to technological developments.

Human resources are a useful factor in achieving company expectations. Labor is useful for deciding the chronology of the production process even though the duties and responsibilities of the workforce are transferred with increasingly developing technology. Therefore, companies need to maximize human resources because they describe phenomenal events and asset management for the survival of the company.

One of the factors that can affect the success rate of a company is employee performance. Employee performance is an important component not only because it is directly related to employee income within a certain period, but also because there is life for the survival of the company.

To develop employee performance, one of which is training according to company needs. Training is needed to maximize the quality of employees and is an important factor in business competition. Rapid technological developments within a company must be balanced by developing human resources to overcome the wheels of the company.

One company that is aware of the importance of the training program is Toko Haimart in Boalemo Regency. Toko Haimart is a trading company located in Boalemo Regency, Gorontalo Province. Toko Haimart conducts training programs for all employees. This training program is provided to all employees to maximize their performance. There are two training programs conducted, namely basic training and capacity building training for each employee. Basic training is carried out for approximately one week at the central Haimart Store, this training is mandatory for all new employees. Meanwhile, employee capacity building training is conducted for all employees who are already in their respective departments. This training is carried out so that employees can develop their abilities by the sections that have been determined by the owner of the Haimart Store in Boalemo Regency.

Even though training has been carried out for all employees, there are still some employees who make mistakes in their work. For example, at the cashier's desk there are still employees who are wrong in returning the buyer's remaining money, in the packaging of goods and the placement of goods there are still things that are not neatly packaged and the goods are still not properly placed, then when sending goods there are still things that are not on time, so that at the time of evaluation there are still employees who are wrong in

completing their work. Where, this problem can affect the development of the Haimart Store. Things like this show that the performance of employees at the Haimart Store in Boalemo Regency is still not optimal.

Management is a series of activities consisting of planning, implementing, monitoring, and controlling to achieve a certain goal that has been targeted through the utilization of human resources and other sources.

Management is the art of getting work done through other people [9]. This definition places more emphasis on a manager where a manager is tasked with managing and directing other people to achieve organizational goals using the human resources found in the company or organization.

Management functions, namely as follows:

1. Planning (planning)

Is a process that involves the efforts made to anticipate future trends in determining the right strategy and tactics to realize the goals and objectives of the organization. Among the current trends in the business world, for example, how to plan an environmentally friendly business, how to design a business organization that can compete in global competition, and so on.

The planning function is as follows:

- a. Setting business goals and targets.
- b. Formulate strategies to achieve these business goals and targets.
- c. Determine the resources needed.
- d. Setting standards or indicators of success in achieving business goals and targets.

2. Organizing

Is a process that concerns how the strategies and tactics that have been formulated in planning are designed in an appropriate and strong organizational structure, conducive system and organizational environment, and can ensure that all parties in the organization can work effectively and efficiently to achieve organizational goals.

The organizing function is as follows:

- a. Allocate resources, formulate and assign tasks, and establish necessary procedures.
- b. Establish an organizational structure that shows lines of authority and responsibility.
- c. Recruitment, selection, training, and human resource/labor development activities.
- d. The activity of placing human resources in the most appropriate position.

3. Implementation (Direction)

It is the process of implementing the program so that it can be implemented by all parties in the organization as well as the process of motivating so that all parties can carry out their responsibilities with full awareness and high productivity.

The implementation function is as follows:

- a. Implementing leadership processes and providing motivation to the workforce so they can work effectively and efficiently in achieving goals.
- b. Give assignments and routine explanations about work.
- c. Explain the policies set

4. Control or Supervision (Controlling)

It is a process carried out to ensure that all series of activities that have been planned, organized and implemented can run according to the expected targets even though various changes occur in the environment the business world is facing.

The supervisory function is as follows:

- a. Evaluate success in achieving business goals and targets according to predetermined indicators.
- b. Take steps to clarify and correct any discrepancies that may be found.
- c. Perform various alternative solutions to various problems related to achieving business goals and targets.

Human resource management is the science and art of knowing the relationships and roles of the workforce so that they can effectively and efficiently help achieve company, employee and community goals.

The objectives of human resource management are as follows:

- 1) Provide management considerations in making HR policies.
- 2) Implement and maintain all HR policies and procedures.
- 3) Assist in developing the direction and strategy of the organization or company.
- 4) Provide support from certain conditions that can assist line managers in achieving the goals of an organization or company.
- 5) Handling various crises and difficult situations between workers and companies or organizations.
- 6) Provide a medium of communication between workers and companies or organizations
- 7) Maintaining organizational standards and values in HR management.

Training is part of education that concerns the learning process to acquire and improve skills outside the applicable education system, in a relatively short time with a method that prioritizes training rather than theory .

The training objectives are as follows:

- 1) Improve employee performance
- 2) Employees who perform unsatisfactorily due to a lack of skills are prime candidates for training.
- 3) Updating the skills of employees in line with technological advances
- 4) Through training (trainers) ensure that employees can apply new technology effectively.
- 5) Reducing learning time for new employees to be competent on the job. New employees often do not master the skills and abilities needed to become "job complete", namely being able to achieve the expected output and quality standards.

The training indicators can be divided into five indicators as follows:

- 1) Instructor
- 2) Reminding that training is generally oriented towards improving skills, the trainers selected to provide training materials must have adequate qualifications under their fields, professional and competent, namely training instructors must have adequate qualifications or competence, be able to motivate participants and need feedback come back.
- 3) Trainee

- 4) Training participants must of course be selected based on certain requirements and appropriate qualifications. Here the characteristics of the participants can be seen from how enthusiastic the participants are in participating in the training and how they want to pay attention to every detail of the training provided.
- 5) Method
- 6) The training method will ensure that effective human resource training activities take place if they are appropriate to the type of material and the abilities of the trainees. The training method should be compatible with the type of training and the training material being implemented.
- 7) Material
- 8) Human resource training is material or curriculum following the objectives of human resource training to be achieved by the company. The training material is expected to increase the ability of its employees and the suitability of the training material with the objectives of the training.
- 9) Benefits of training
- 10) Training requires defined benefits, particularly about preparing action plans and setting targets, as well as the expected results of the training being held. The purpose of a training is to improve the skills and understanding of the work ethic of the trainees.

Performance comes from the word Job Performance or Actual Performance, namely work performance or actual performance of an employee or employees, so the notion of performance is the result of work in quality or quantity achieved by an employee or employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him [11].

Performance is the result of work achieved by every employee or employees in developing their duties and work that comes from the organization or company. Performance is also a result of work produced by individuals through the process of an organization or company that can be measured concretely and compared with the standards set by the organization or company.

Factors that affect performance according to include:

- 1) Employee internal factors, namely factors that come from within the employee itself and are divided into competence, knowledge (education), talent, work experience, physical and psychological conditions, work motivation, work enthusiasm, and job satisfaction. After being influenced by the internal environment and external environment, these internal factors determine employee performance. So, it can be assumed that the higher the internal factors, the higher the employee's performance. Conversely, the lower these factors, the lower the performance.
- 2) Internal organizational environmental factors, in carrying out their duties, employees need the support of the organization where they work. This support affects the level of employee performance, for example, the use of technology, otherwise if the compensation and organizational work climate are bad, employee performance will decrease. Other internal organizational environmental factors such as management systems, support resources needed to complete work, leadership, co-workers, and training.

2. Methods

The approach in this study uses a mixed-method research approach. A qualitative approach is research that crosses several disciplines, science, and material, involving a deep understanding of human behavior and the reasons that govern this human behavior.

This research uses descriptive research type. Descriptive research is research that is intended to investigate the circumstances, conditions, or other things that have been mentioned, the results of which are presented in the form of a research report. **Types of descriptive research we used is survey research, collecting data from a large number of respondents using observation, interviews, and documentation.**

3. Results

The research results show that:

- 1) Implementation of training in improving employee performance, with the following indicators:

Training Benefits

"In my opinion, the implementation of a training course has benefits for the employees themselves, because with the implementation of this training program, each employee is given knowledge and experience that is appropriate to their work so that they can increase productivity, quality of work and improve the quality of work results and can reduce errors in carrying out the work done. given"

Training Instructor

"The trainers or instructors for this training program are myself and the shop heads at each Haimart store. I as the owner of the Haimart Store and as a provider of basic training materials for prospective employees and for Shop heads as a provider of employee capacity building training"

Training Methods

"The method we use is to encourage the participants and provide basic training materials for new employees. This training is held for one month to find out the capabilities of each employee or the trainees themselves. This training is provided by the owner of the Haimart Store directly. In the following, we place them according to the section in the Haimart Store that is in accordance with the abilities they have, then provide employee capacity building training according to the section occupied, this training is given by the heads of the Haimart Store"

Training materials

"We provide material to prospective trainees in the form of basic training material because with this training material it can add to the knowledge of employees or the trainees themselves, for example material on packaging and placing goods according to size and type, at the cashier's section the material is given how to find out every inventory of goods in the Haimart Store, procedures for opening and closing the Store, how to serve customers properly and much more according to the sections in the Haimart Store"

Training Participants

"For the training participants themselves, all employees at the Haimart Store, both new employees and existing employees, are in their respective departments. Concerns all employees"

because there are two types of training provided, namely basic training and capacity building training”

2) Factors Affecting Employee Performance, With the Following Indicators:

Employee internal factors

“When carrying out their work there are still employees who make mistakes, this is because at the time of providing material or practice in the training program there are still employees who find it difficult to understand the training material delivered by the instructor or training provider”

Organizational internal environmental factors

“The facilities at the Haimart Store are still incomplete, for example the computer used during the training in the cashier section is still lacking. Where, the trainees only use one computer when participating in the training, this also has an impact on the process of implementing the training because the trainees have to take turns using the computer when attending the training provided”

4. Discussion

Implementation of training in improving employee performance

Based on the results of interviews with several informants, it can be concluded that:

- a. The benefits of implementing training, the implementation of training is very beneficial for the employees themselves, especially in improving the quality of work, abilities or skills possessed by each employee and can increase the knowledge and work experience of employees, especially for new employees who have no experience in completing their work. The benefits of training are not only felt by new employees, but this is also beneficial for old employees, especially employees who have been placed in departments at the Haimart Store. The benefit for old employees is that with this training employees can hone their skills according to the part they have occupied. The implementation of training at Haimart Stores not only has benefits for employees but also benefits for the Haimart Store itself, one of which is that Haimart Stores can produce quality employees who have the ability and have good quality work.
- b. Instructors or trainers, for employee training programs do not bring in speakers from outside but the instructors or trainers in providing this training are the owners and heads of Haimart Stores directly. This is done to reduce additional costs in providing training materials, training is given directly by the owner so that he can find out firsthand the abilities possessed by employees and by what the company wants and can be placed in parts that have been determined according to their abilities and skills possessed.
- c. The method of implementing the training, method used in implementing this training is to divide the training into two parts, namely basic training for new employees and capacity building training for permanent employees. Basic training is given directly by the owner of the Haimart Store to all trainees or new employees themselves, this is done so that the owner of the Haimart Store can find out the abilities or skills possessed by every employee in the Haimart Store. Furthermore, the owner of the Haimart Store places employees in the section according to their abilities to continue further training, namely training to develop the abilities of each employee. This training is given directly by the shop heads at each Haimart Store.

- d. Training material, for the training material itself is given by the existing section at the Haimart Store, in the provision of this training which is carried out first the training participants are given training material as a basis for them to carry out direct practice. The material provided includes material on good packaging of goods and placing them according to their size and type, then training materials on how to find out the hospitalization of each item and how to serve customers properly and correctly. All training provided must be attended by all prospective employees, by carrying out a training both shop owners and heads who as training providers at Haimart Stores can find out the abilities possessed by each employee in completing their work and responsibilities. Furthermore, these employees will be placed in sections according to their abilities. Then this ability will be developed through capacity building training given in accordance with the parts they occupy until they really master the job given. With this capacity development training, each employee can develop the skills they have so that they can affect their performance, this also directly affects the development of Haimart Stores.
- e. Training participants, training participants are people who come or people who take part in the training program at the Haimart Store, this is the training participants in the implementation of the training program who become training participants are all employees at the Haimart Store. Both new employees and employees who have been placed in predetermined sections, this is because there are two types of training provided, namely basic training for new employees, capacity building training for employees who are already in predetermined sections.

Factors Affecting Employee Performance

Based on the results of interviews with several informants, it was found that:

- a. Employee Internal Factors
One of the factors that influence performance is the internal factor of employees, especially the knowledge possessed by each employee in a company or organization. However, there are still employees who are still lacking in knowledge after attending the training provided, one of the factors causing the lack of employee knowledge about employee training is that during the implementation of the training there are still employees who have difficulty understanding the material presented by the instructor during the training, so that this can affect its performance. This can be seen from the evaluation of employee performance where there are still employees who make mistakes in completing the work assigned to them. If this is allowed to continue without the right solution, it will directly affect the performance of every employee at the Haimart Store.
- b. Organizational Internal Environmental Factors
Organizational internal environmental factors are also included in factors that affect performance. Where, one of them is the completeness of existing facilities and infrastructure in a company or organization. For example, the completeness of facilities and infrastructure is very much needed in the implementation of training, this is certainly very much needed to make it easier for training instructors to provide training materials and provide direct training practice. However, the facilities and infrastructure at Haimart Stores are not fully complete, training facilities, lack of

facilities at Haimart Stores. Among them, a special place has not been held for the implementation of training, there is still a lack of computers used during training and a lack of tools used when packing food or products. This will most likely affect the performance of each individual. If this is left without the right solution from the training provider then this will certainly have an impact on employee performance and employee work quality, for this reason a solution or the right method is needed to overcome obstacles in implementing this training. Especially for the cashier who has to master all the systems on the computer and for the place of implementation it is needed so as not to interfere with the implementation of the training given at that time. With the existence of complete facilities and infrastructure during the training, of course the training will be carried out properly and of course it will definitely affect the performance of each employee.

Several authors (Flint et al., 2008; Gosling et al., 2016; Jia & Lamming, 2012) have explored the effect, motivation and context of sustainability training, knowledge sharing among companies and organizational learning theory. Njuguna (2009) pointed out that knowledge obtained through trainings or other learning activities on an individual level needs to be spread to other team members and to the organizational level. In this regard, according to Probst & Buchel (1997) in Kristina et al., (2023), changes in the knowledge and values to improve a company's capability to solve problems describes the process of intra-organizational learning. Intra-organizational learning can be defined as *the sum total of individual and collective learning through training programs, experience, experimentation and work interactions within the organization*. Thus, sustainability trainings provided by focal companies can be seen as a tool used to generate intra-organizational learning. Mariotti (2012) described inter-organizational learning as a complex phenomenon and distinguishes between the creation of collective knowledge, the creation of network rules of interaction, and knowledge acquisition and transfer.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Training or training is an activity that aims to improve and develop attitudes, behavior, skills, and knowledge so that employees are more skilled and able to carry out their responsibilities better by company standards and wishes. Training is one of the efforts to improve the quality of human resources in the world of work, every employee, both new and those who have worked for a long time, needs to attend training. This is also applied by Haimart store owners who implement training for new employees and old employees, in this case, there is training to improve the performance of employees at Haimart stores and there are also factors that affect performance. Based on the results of the research and the formulation of the research problem, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Implementation of training to improve employee performance:
 - a. The benefits of implementing training, the implementation of training is very beneficial for the employees themselves. Where, can develop the capabilities possessed, and increase the knowledge and work experience of employees.

- b. For the training instructors themselves, they do not bring in speakers from outside but from the Haimart shop itself, namely the owners and heads of the Haimart shop, this is done so as not to increase costs in conducting the training.
 - c. The training method used is to divide the training into two, namely basic training for new employees and capacity building training for employees whose divisions have been assigned.
 - d. The training material provided is by the part that will be occupied when you become an employee at the Haimart Store and is given according to the capabilities of each employee.
 - e. Training participants in the implementation of this training program are all employees at the Haimart Store, both new employees and employees who have been placed in designated sections. This training program must be attended by all employees at the Haimart Store.
2. Factors that influence the performance of Haimart store employees are:
- a. Employee internal factors. One of the factors that influence performance is the internal factor of employees, especially the knowledge possessed by each employee in a company or organization. However, there are still employees who are still lacking in knowledge after attending the training provided, one of the factors causing the lack of employee knowledge about employee training is that during the implementation of the training, there are still employees who have difficulty understanding the material presented by the instructor during the training so that this can affect its performance. This can be seen from the evaluation of employee performance where there are still employees who make mistakes in completing the work given to them. If this is allowed to continue without the right solution, it will directly affect the performance of every employee at the Haimart Store.
 - b. Organizational internal environmental factors. This factor is also included in the factors that affect performance. Where one of them is the completeness of existing facilities and infrastructure in a company or organization. For example, the completeness of facilities and infrastructure is very much needed in the implementation of training, this is certainly very much needed to make it easier for training instructors to provide training materials and provide direct training practice. However, the facilities and infrastructure at Haimart Stores are not fully complete, training facilities, lack of facilities at Haimart Stores. Among them, a special place has not been held for the implementation of training, there is still a lack of computers used during training and a lack of tools used when packing food or products. This will most likely affect the performance of each individual. If this is left without the right solution from the training provider then this will certainly have an impact on employee performance and employee work quality, for this reason a solution or method is needed that is appropriate in overcoming obstacles in the implementation of this training. Especially for the cashier who has to master all the systems on the computer and for the place of implementation it is needed so as not to interfere with the implementation of the training given at that time. With the existence of complete facilities and infrastructure during the training, the training will certainly be carried out properly and of course definitely affect the performance of each employee.

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